

Most suitable locations for large scale PV-driven hydrogen production valleys implementation in Portugal using AHP-GIS combination approach

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ABSTRACT

Leveraging solar resources for hydrogen production represents a key pathway to decarbonization and the advancement of a sustainable energy system. Against this backdrop, the objective of this study is to identify the most suitable locations for the development of large-scale solar-driven hydrogen valleys in Portugal. To achieve this, high-resolution input data were employed in combination with the Analytical Hierarchy Process and Geographic Information Systems to create a land suitability atlas for the country. Furthermore, a techno-economic analysis was conducted to assess the feasibility of implementing such projects in the selected areas, considering hydrogen production potential and costs associated with the electrolyser and the different photovoltaic plants configurations. Results show that the “highly suitable” locations, representing nearly 2% of the total land area -approximately 1665.67 km²-, offer significant potential for hydrogen production. Moreover, for the four selected hotspots, the techno-economic results were very promising, especially at Hotspot 2, near Sines, where the levelized cost of hydrogen is of 2.95 €/kg with a high annual “green” hydrogen production of 2351 tons for 50 MW_{DC} photovoltaic capacity, which means 47 kg for each kW of capacity. This result demonstrates the ability of Portugal to be positioned in the “green” hydrogen market, especially with the existing concurrence from Morocco and Spain and also it supports the energy programs in Portugal for a “green” and sustainable development of the country.

Nomenclature:

GIS	Geographic Information System
MCDM	Multi-Criteria Decision-Making
AHP	Analytic Hierarchy Process
FAHP	Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process
MC-FAHP	Multi-Criteria Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process
FTOPSIS	Fuzzy Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution
FVIKOR	Fuzzy VIKOR
VIKOR	Serbian: Visekriterijumska optimizacija i Kompromisno Resenje
TOPSIS	Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution
SWARA	Step-wise Weight Assessment Ratio Analysis
EDAS	Evaluation based on Distance from Average Solution

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ARAS	Additive Ratio Assessment
WASPAS	Weighted Aggregated Sum Product Assessment
COPRAS	Complex Proportional Assessment
WSM	Weighted Sum Model
BWM	Best-Worst Method
PROMETHEE	Preference Ranking Organization METHod for Enrichment
II	Evaluation, version II
H ₂	Hydrogen
PVH2	Photovoltaic-based hydrogen production
LCOH ₂	Levelized Cost of Hydrogen (\$/kg and €/kg)
kWh/m ²	kilowatt-hour per square meter
kg/kWh	kilogram per kilowatt-hour
\$/kg	Dollar per kilogram

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\$/kW	Dollar per kilowatt
€/kg	Euro per kilogram
€/kW	Euro per kilowatt
km	kilometer
W	Watt
GWh	Gigawatt-hour
AC	Alternating current
DC	Direct current
E_i	Annual electricity production in the year i (kWh/year)
N	Project lifetime
T	Project discount rate
C_E	Investment cost of the photovoltaic plant (cost of electricity production) (\$ and €)
$C_{O\&M}$	Cost of operation & maintenance. (\$ and €)
$C_{Total\ Capital\ Cost}$	Capital expenditures of the photovoltaic plant (\$ and €)
M_{H_2}	Hydrogen production (kg)
C_{conv}	Cost of AC/DC converter (\$ and €)
C_{elec}	Electrolyzer investment cost (\$ and €)
C_{el}	Capital cost of the electrolyzer (\$ and €)
C_{rep}	Replacement cost (\$ and €)
$C_{el,u}$	Unit cost of the electrolyzer (\$ and €)
$K_{el,th}$	Theoretical energy required (kWh/kg)
η_{ele}	Electrolyser efficiency
PV	Photovoltaic
PEM	Proton exchange membrane
HHV_{H_2}	Hydrogen higher heating value (kWh/kg)

1. Introduction

The global reliance on fossil fuels has increasingly raised concerns over energy security, especially following recent geopolitical tensions such as the Russian war in Ukraine. Many countries, especially Europe, reduced their energy imports from Russia [1], contributing to an energy shortage in the region. Shifting to renewable sources—such as solar, wind, and hydropower—offers a viable solution that ensures energy security and supports the low-carbon transition [2]. By 2022, oil and natural gas were the dominant energy sources in Europe, accounting for 32% and 25%, respectively, of the total energy supply of 1818 Mtoe. In contrast, hydropower accounted for only 2.6%, biofuel and waste for 10.7%, and renewable energy for 5.4%, according to the International Energy Agency (IEA) [3]. Wind and solar photovoltaic (PV) contributed 38.9% and 17.5%, respectively, to the total renewable electricity generated, which reached 1430 TWh in the same year [3]. For the present case study, Portugal's total energy supply in 2023 amounted to 18.72 Mtoe, with oil as the dominant source (45%), followed by natural gas (20.3%), hydropower (5.5%), biofuel and waste (18.7%), and only 10% from renewable energy (wind, solar, etc.) [4]. Moreover, in 2024 the total renewable energy installed capacity stood at 20.476 GW, with PV totaling 5.808 GW, hydropower with a capacity of 8.347 GW and wind energy with 5.538 GW (5.558 GW onshore and 25 MW offshore), the bioenergy with a 709 MW capacity and also with the smallest capacity the geothermal energy with 29 MW [5]. Additionally, the government has a plan to increase renewable energy production from 14.1 GWh in 2019 to 27.4 GWh by 2030. Solar resources are expected to increase from 0.9 GWh to 9 GWh over the same period, according to IEA report [6]. However, the main challenge is energy storage, particularly storing excess energy during peak production for later use. Electrolysis offers an opportunity to store this energy by converting it into “green” hydrogen [7]. Additionally, “green” hydrogen can be used for various applications (fuel for fuel-cell electric cars, production of synthetic fuels, blend with natural gas, etc.) and serves as a reliable energy vector, all with zero CO₂ emissions [8].

Furthermore, producing “green” hydrogen from renewable sources—such as solar, wind, and hydropower—enables countries to exploit the diversity of their renewable resources more effectively by prioritizing hydrogen production in regions where development is most competitive [9]. However, the deployment of such projects involves addressing multiple technical, economic, environmental, and social

criteria, including, among other factors, the availability and reliability of renewable energy fed into the electrolyzer. Against this backdrop, many researchers have conducted studies using different multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) methods to identify the most suitable zones based on different criteria and scenarios, and for different resources, in various countries and regions for “green” hydrogen power plants.

In the case of Morocco [10], Amrani et al. developed an Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) matrix combined with Geographic Information Systems (GIS) tools to identify high-suitability zones for PV-based and Concentrated Solar Power (CSP)-based hydrogen projects. They found that 20.3% and 7.5% of the Moroccan area are highly suitable for PV-based and CSP-based hydrogen production, respectively, with good leveled cost of hydrogen (LCOH₂) values: 4.972 \$/kg (4.594 €/kg) for PV-H₂ and 9.816 \$/kg (9.070 €/kg) for CSP-H₂. Taoufik et al. [11] further studied Morocco, especially the Souss-Massa region, using AHP and FAHP combined with GIS tools to locate the best site for a large-scale hydrogen PV plant. They found areas of 61.29 km² (high suitability), 5347 km² (moderate), 45108.57 km² (low), and 328.88 km² (very low) from the FAHP result. The estimated annual hydrogen production using a 289 MW PV farm was 12 500 tons, with a low LCOH₂ of 2.9 \$/kg (2.68 €/kg). Other studies also used MCDM to identify the best locations for renewable energy power, Jbaili et al. [12] studied hybrid solar technology (PV + CSP) in Morocco using AHP and GIS to develop suitability maps for multiple scenarios (dry and wet cooling). For dry cooling, the results showed 7.2% limited suitability, 24.1% suitable, 36.5% highly suitable, and 32.2% excellent. For wet cooling, the results were 10.8%, 26%, 52.1%, and 11.2%, respectively. About 26.5% of Morocco was considered restricted. In Turkey [13], specifically in Kayseri, Karipoğlu et al. determined the high-suitability zones for solar hydrogen refueling stations using eight sub-criteria and GIS tools. They identified a highly suitable area of 7.3 km² (4.3% of the total study area). In South Korea, for the Congwo-do region, Yum et al. [14] used the AHP method combined with GIS to determine the most suitable zone for a solar-based smart hydrogen energy plant. They found suitability classes of 11.29%, 24.92%, 43.93%, 16.12%, and 3.74% for non-suitable, low, moderate, high, and very high suitability, respectively. In Algeria, especially the Adrar province, Messaoudi et al. [15] studied the suitability of large-scale wind power hydrogen refueling stations using GIS and AHP methods. They found high, medium, low, and not suitable zones representing 2.95%, 54.59%, 1.12%, and 41.34% of the area, respectively. Still for Algeria, Messaoudi et al. [16] created suitability maps for solar hydrogen production using AHP combined with GIS. The results showed high, moderate, low, and very low suitability zones representing 0.49%, 6.68%, 60.75%, and 10.34% of the total study area, respectively. The restriction (unsuitable) zone accounted for 21.74%. In Afghanistan, Mostafaeipour et al. [17] used eleven criteria to identify the best province for installing a wind hydrogen station. They applied multiple MCDM methods (SWARA, EDAS, ARAS, TOPSIS, and VIKOR) and found that Herat is the best province, with an estimated production of 41.4 tons/year using a 900 kW wind turbine. In Uzbekistan, Xuan et al. [18] studied thirteen provinces to determine the best location for a large-scale PV hydrogen plant using various MCDM methods (SWARA, WASPAS, COPRAS, EDAS, and WSM) and 10 criteria. They identified Bukhara as the best province, with an estimated 1 MW plant capacity producing, respectively, 1539.2 MWh and 24.92 tons of electricity and hydrogen annually. In Southern Thailand, Ali et al. [19] developed a suitability map for solar hydrogen plants using GIS-AHP. They classified the area into three classes: high suitability (4302.06 km²), moderate (3550.37 km²), and low (321.36 km²). In Pakistan, Amjad et al. [20] determined the suitable sites for solar hydrogen using the Best-Worst Method (BWM) combined with GIS tools. They found that the most suitable locations are in Baluchistan Province. Flora [21] examined Cameroon using AHP, FAHP, and MC-FAHP methods combined with GIS tools to identify suitable areas for large-scale solar hydrogen farms. The study found 42% of the total area to be restricted, and from the MC-FAHP result, 13.66%, 40.28%, and 3.66% were classified as

Fig. 1. Flowchart of our study.

suitable, highly suitable, and most suitable, respectively.

For our case study in Portugal, and apart from the MCDM methods, other studies have been carried out to evaluate hydrogen production using different technologies. Silva et al. [22] processed meteorological data from 89 stations across mainland Portugal to create TMY files, which were then used to simulate and calculate PV-based hydrogen production for each station location. By applying interpolation using GIS tools, they developed the first PV–hydrogen atlas of Portugal, including the levelized cost of hydrogen (LCOH₂). Their results showed a minimum LCOH₂ of 3.476 €/kg with a high specific annual hydrogen production of 36.56 kg/kWp. In another study, Attiaoui et al. [23] used data from 88 meteorological stations to simulate and calculate wind–hydrogen production across the country. Using kriging interpolation with GIS tools, they produced the first wind–hydrogen atlas for mainland Portugal. Their results revealed promising potential, with a specific annual production of up to 113 kg/kW and a minimum LCOH₂ of 3.258 €/kg. These findings confirm the strong potential of both PV and wind hydrogen production in Portugal.

The objective of this study is to identify the most suitable areas for building a solar photovoltaic-based hydrogen power plant on mainland Portugal using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) combined with GIS tools. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study in Portugal to apply this integrated approach, providing guidance for strategic planning and site selection for “green” hydrogen development. Based on this integrated approach, a suitability atlas was created to classify areas as “Highly suitable”, “Suitable”, “Moderately suitable”, or “Marginally suitable” while an exclusion atlas identified regions unsuitable for development. The analysis indicates that the majority of the territory

(82.26%) is unsuitable, with 0.13% marginally suitable, 3.40% suitable, 11.62% moderately suitable, and 1.89% highly suitable.

To further evaluate hydrogen production in Portugal, we selected four hotspots in the “Highly suitable” areas and simulated hydrogen power stations with 50 MW_{DC} PV capacity. Each hotspot was evaluated using three PV technologies: fixed system, single-axis tracking, and dual-axis tracking systems, all supplying a PEM electrolyzer. From the techno-economic analysis, it was found that Hotspot 2 in Sines had the highest annual hydrogen production of 2351 tons for 50 MW_{DC} photovoltaic capacity, which means 47 kg for each kW of capacity, with the lower levelized cost of hydrogen (LCOH₂) of 2.95 €/kg using single-axis tracking systems, which is a promising indicator for the future of hydrogen production in Portugal.

The rest of the manuscript is divided into three main sections: methodology, results and conclusions. The methodology section is the main one and is further divided into five sub-sections. The first discusses the study area, evaluate the criteria used, and the identification of restriction zones. This is followed by the AHP method and the simulation inputs, including the PV equation module and the techno-economic equations.

2. Methodology

Five main criteria and thirteen sub-criteria were considered to identify the most suitable locations for PVH2 power plant development. The AHP was integrated with GIS tools for spatial analysis, while fourteen exclusion factors were applied to designate areas as unsuitable. The four most promising sites were subsequently selected, and large-scale

Fig. 2. Area of study - Portugal is highlighted in green. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

hydrogen production was simulated for each location. A techno-economic analysis was then conducted to assess the feasibility of the PVH2 plants. The complete methodological workflow is presented in Fig. 1.

After data collection, all datasets were integrated into ArcGIS Pro software, one of the most famous and powerful GIS software packages and used for two main objectives. The first objective was to create exclusion zones using fourteen factors. To do this, specific tools were used: buffer tools to create buffer areas (for waterways, roads, and railways), and the raster calculator to identify exclusion areas based on GHI values and slope. After that, the merge tool was applied to combine all these separated raster areas into one layer.

The second main objective was to identify suitability levels based on AHP results. First, distances from all sub-criteria (water resources, accessibility, and economic sub-criteria) were calculated using the Euclidean distance tool. Then, all sub-criteria were reclassified into four classes using the reclassify tool. Finally, the raster calculator was used to weight each pixel for each class of the sub-criterion layers and merge them to obtain the final suitability map. All these processes were carried out using the ERST 1989 TM06 projection and resolution of 30 arc seconds (~1 km).

This section is organized into five subsections to provide a clear presentation of the methodology: Study area, describing the geographical position of Portugal; Criteria evaluation, detailing the main and sub-criteria used for site selection; Unsuitable areas, outlining the exclusion factors applied to eliminate non-viable locations; AHP method, explaining the methodology and its integration with GIS for spatial analysis; and Techno-economic analysis, presenting the calculation framework employed for the techno-economic assessment of the PVH2 plants.

2.1. Study area

Portugal is considered one of the most suitable European countries for solar power plant projects [24], especially in the southern part of Europe. It has a total mainland surface area of more than 89 000 square kilometers, overlooking the Atlantic Ocean. The country receives a maximum Global Horizontal irradiation (GHI) of over ~1900 kWh/m²/year [25]. For all these reasons, Portugal was selected as the case study to determine the best zones for a large-scale PV solar

Global Horizontal Irradiation (GHI) in Portugal

Fig. 3. Global horizontal irradiation in Portugal.

hydrogen power plant across the entire mainland. Fig. 2 presents Portugal's geographical position among European countries.

Table 1
Data sources used to develop the criteria used in the study.

Data bases		References
Solar	Global horizontal irradiance	[25]
Orography	Digital elevation model	[26]
Water accessibility	Dams	[28]
	Rivers	[29]
	Sea edges	
	Underground water	
Economic factors	Population data	[27]
	Electricity grid	[30]
	Gas pipeline	
	Ports	[31]
Accessibility	Cities	
	Roads and railways	[29]

2.2. Criteria evaluation

This section represents a central component of the study, emphasizing the criteria employed to systematically assess and prioritize the appropriate zones for the establishment of a large-scale PV solar hydrogen production plant. An extensive review of the literature was undertaken to identify five main criteria and thirteen sub-criteria, ensuring a robust and well-grounded assessment framework. These criteria provide the basis for a systematic evaluation of potential locations, thereby enhancing the reliability of the site selection process. Each criterion is examined in detail in the following subsections.

2.2.1. Climate

Global horizontal irradiation (GHI) represents the most critical factor in determining the optimal locations for the PVH2 power plant [10]. Since GHI directly drives the efficiency of the PV system and, consequently, the output of the electrolysis system, it is crucial to prioritize areas with the highest solar potential to maximize “green” hydrogen production. A 24-year average dataset from SolarGIS [25] was integrated within the GIS framework to generate a comprehensive GHI map (Fig. 3), enabling the precise identification of the most suitable sites for plant development.

2.2.2. Orography

The PVH2 power plant requires a relatively flat surface to ensure flexibility and economic efficiency. For this reason, many studies have

considered the slope factor to identify suitable zones (Table 1). In this study, a digital elevation data from the NASA Shuttle Radar Topographic Mission (SRTM) 1 arc-second global [26] has been utilized. Using GIS tools, a slope map has been generated, as well as a surface aspect map to identify and exclude unsuitable areas. Fig. 4 presents the elevation and slope maps.

2.2.3. Water accessibility

Water availability constitutes a critical criterion for the selection of potential sites, as water is essential for hydrogen production. Access to water directly impacts the feasibility of a project, as sites located farther from water sources incur additional capital expenditures associated with water supply infrastructure. In this study, four categories of water sources were considered: aquifers, dams, seawater, and natural waterways. Distances to these sources were quantified using GIS-based spatial analysis and integrated as sub-criteria within the overall site suitability assessment.

2.2.4. Economic and accessibility

Other two criteria were incorporated into the site selection process. The first is economic, which plays a crucial role in the utilization and distribution of the hydrogen produced. Four sub-criteria were considered: electricity grid, gas pipeline, port proximity, and population density. Distances to the electricity grid, gas pipeline, and ports were calculated using GIS tools, while population data, obtained from the Portuguese National Institute of Statistics (*Instituto Nacional de Estatística*, Portugal) [27], were aggregated at the district level. The second criterion, Accessibility, constitutes a critical factor influencing both the feasibility and overall cost-efficiency of PVH2 plant development. Proximity to transportation networks—including primary and secondary roads, railways, and major urban centers—is essential for the delivery of equipment and materials, as well as for ongoing operation and maintenance activities. Sites located far from existing infrastructure incur additional costs due to the construction of new access roads. Distances to these accessibility elements were quantified through GIS-based spatial analysis and incorporated in the overall site suitability assessment. All maps related to water availability, economic factors, and accessibility are presented in Fig. 5.

The following table presents the data sources used to develop the sub-criteria shown in Figs. 3–5.

Fig. 4. Elevations and Slope maps of Portugal.

a) Water accessibility

b) Economic

c) Infrastructure

Fig. 5. Maps for: a) Water accessibility; b) Economic factors; c) Accessibility.

2.3. Restriction zone/unsuitable area

Before identifying the suitability zones and making decisions, it is important to consider the restricted areas. This section discusses the restriction factors and presents the restriction (exclusion) map. Many studies have applied wide restrictions for PV and PV-hydrogen power plants, which are listed in Table 2.

Based on a comprehensive review of the literature, previous studies, and a thorough evaluation of the case study context, a set of extensive exclusion factors was selected. The selected exclusion factors encompass several environmental, economic, and infrastructural considerations. Areas with GHI below 1450 kWh/m²/year [34], slopes exceeding 15% [34], and north-facing aspects were classified as unsuitable [37]. Dams

and waterways are also excluded areas with a 500 m buffer zone [33]. Economic restrictions include building surfaces, the electricity grid, and gas pipelines, each with a 500 m buffer zone [20]. Accessibility restrictions include roads and railways with a 300 m buffer zone [38], and airports with a 2500 m buffer area [36]. Protected areas (Natura 2000 and UNESCO reserves) and forests are also excluded areas, [20]. Additionally, military zones with a 3000 m buffer area are also excluded.

Using GIS tools in combination with the defined exclusion factors, an exclusion mask was generated, indicating that 82.26% (73 917 km²) of mainland Portugal is unsuitable for PV-hydrogen power plant development. Consequently, 17.74% (15 185 km²) of the territory remains potentially suitable for project deployment. Fig. 6 represents the resulting unsuitable/restriction map.

Table 2
Restriction factors for PVH2 and PV power plant used in previous studies.

Previous literature studies	[20]	[32]	[33]	[34]	[35]	[12]	[36]
Factors	Unsuitable area/retraction with buffer zone (n = restriction without buffer area)						
GHI	<1700 kWh/m ² /year	—	—	<1450 kWh/m ² /year	<4.5 kWh/m ² /year	1700 kWh/m ² /year	<1300 kWh/m ² /year
Slope %	—	>20	—	>15	—	>5°	>10
Dams and lakes with distance in km	—	≤0.1	≤0.5	≤3	≤0.5	≤0.1	≤0.1
Waterways with distance in km	—	≤0.1	≤0.5	—	≤0.5	≤0.1	≤0.1
Building with distance in km	n	≤0.5	—	—	—	—	—
Forest with distance in km	n	n	—	—	—	—	n
Electricity Grid with distance in km	≤0.5 & >10	—	—	—	≤0.8	—	≤0.25 & > 30
Protected area with distance in km	n	—	≤2	≤2	—	—	n
Railways with distance in km	≤0.5 & >10	—	≤0.5	—	—	≤0.05	≤0.5 & >10
Road with distance in km	≤0.5 & >10	≤0.1	≤0.5	—	≤0.5	≤0.1	<0.5 & >10
Military with distance in km areas	—	—	≤1.5	—	—	n	—
Airport with distance in km	—	—	≤0.5	—	≤3	—	≤2.5
Big cities with distance in km	≤0.1	—	—	—	≤5	—	≤2 & >45
Gas Pipelines with distance in km	—	≤0.07	≤0.07	—	—	—	—
Surface aspect	—	North & Northeast & Northwest	—	—	—	—	—
Others	Hydrogen generation potential, etc.	Seasonal crops, marshland, etc.	Fault lines, historical sites, etc.	Wildlife, hunting areas, shooting areas.	Flood-sensitive areas, etc.	—	Population density, required plant area

2.4. The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)

The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), originally developed by Thomas Saaty [39], is widely recognized as an effective technique for addressing multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) problems. It has been extensively applied to identify suitable regions for the implementation of renewable energy power plants, including solar, wind, and hydrogen facilities, among others [19]. AHP proves to be a powerful method, allowing pairwise comparisons between criteria or sub-criteria using a scaling system proposed by Saaty, as presented in Table 3. Based on these comparisons, an AHP matrix is formed, facilitating the systematic ranking of all factors and the calculation of relative weights for each criterion and sub-criterion.

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & \dots & S_{1n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ S_{n1} = 1/S_{1n} & \dots & S_{nn} \end{bmatrix} \tag{1}$$

After the comparison matrix, to calculate the weight coefficients: First, calculate the normalization using:

$$\bar{S}_{ij} = \frac{S_{ij}}{\sum_{j=1}^n S_{ij}}, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, n \tag{2}$$

\bar{S}_{ij} represents the normalized values

Next, the weights are calculated by:

$$w_i = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \bar{S}_{ij} \tag{3}$$

However, to ensure the reliability of the AHP results, the consistency of the pairwise comparisons must be carefully evaluated. The Consistency Ratio (CR) quantifies the degree of consistency in the judgments,

with a value below 10% generally considered acceptable, indicating that the derived weights are coherent and reliable. The CR can be calculated using the following formula:

$$CR = \frac{CI}{RI}, \tag{4}$$

CI is the Consistency Index, which can be calculated using Equation (5), and RI is defined by Saaty in Table 4 [39]:

$$CI = \frac{\lambda_{max} - n}{n - 1}, \tag{5}$$

here λ_{max} is the eigenvalue of the pairwise comparison, n is the number of indicator/criterion.

2.5. Simulation input and economic equations

This part discusses the simulation of a PV-hydrogen power plant at the four best locations, and is divided into two subsections: hydrogen production and economic equations.

2.5.1. Hydrogen production

To simulate hydrogen production the SAM (System Advisor Model) tool has been used to generate electricity production data using three scenarios for each location. After that, we used Equation (7) below to calculate hydrogen production.

The electricity production was calculated using the following equation, where GHI is the Global Horizontal Irradiation, η_{PV} is the PV module efficiency, and η_{CE} is the conditioning efficiency [11]:

$$E = GHI \cdot \eta_{PV} \cdot \eta_{CE}. \tag{6}$$

However, Portugal has many PV power plants. The Morgavel solar

Fig. 6. PVH2 Restriction map.

PV power plant, located near Sines in the south of Lisbon, has a total capacity of 46 MW_{AC} [40]. For this reason, and using the SAM simulator, we simulated a 50 MW_p plant at four suitable locations in Portugal to evaluate three technologies: fixed system, single-axis tracking system, and dual-axis tracking system. All specific parameters of the power plant are presented in Table 5.

To simulate hydrogen production, we need to use the following equation, where M_{H_2} is the hydrogen production (kg), E is the electricity production from PV power plant (kWh), η_{ele} is the electrolyser efficiency (75%), HHV_{H_2} is the hydrogen higher heating value (39.4 kWh/kg).

$$M_{H_2} = \frac{\eta_{ele} \times E}{HHV_{H_2}} \quad (7)$$

2.5.2. Economic analysis

This part discusses the most important metric to evaluate the reliability of the hydrogen power plant. The levelized cost of hydrogen (LCOH₂) is widely used in other studies [41] for economic assessment

and is calculated by the following equation, where C_E is the investment cost of the PV power plant, C_{elec} is the electrolyzer investment cost, $M_{H_2,i}$ is the annual hydrogen production at year i , T and N are the discount rate and the project lifetime taken as 6% and 25 years, respectively:

$$LCOH_2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (C_E + C_{elec}) \times (1 + T)^{-i}}{\sum_{i=1}^N M_{H_2,i} \times (1 + T)^{-i}}, \quad (8)$$

the investment C_E cost of the PV plant is calculated by the next equation [10]:

$$C_E = C_{mod} + C_{BoS} + C_{O\&MofPV} + C_{Tr}, \quad (9)$$

here C_{mod} is the PV module cost, C_{BoS} is the balance of the system, $C_{O\&MofPV}$ is the operation and maintenance cost, and C_{Tr} is the tracking system cost (not considered for fixed systems). The PEM electrolyzer

Table 3
The fundamental scale between indicators.

Intensity of Importance	Definition	Explanation
1	Equal importance	Two parameters/criteria contribute in equal terms to the objective
3	Moderate importance	Experience and judgment moderately favor one parameter/criterion over another
5	Essential or strong importance	Experience and judgement strongly favor one parameter/criterion over another
7	Very strong importance	A parameter/criterion is strongly favored and its dominance demonstrated in practice
9	Extreme importance	The evidence favoring one parameter/criterion over another is of the highest possible order of affirmation
2,4,6,8	Intermediate values between the two adjacent judgments	When compromises are needed between the previous intensities

cost C_{elec} is calculated by the following equation:

$$C_{elec} = C_{el} + C_{O\&MofEl} + C_{rep},$$

here C_{el} is the PEM electrolyzer investment cost, calculated using the equation below, $C_{O\&MofEl}$ is the operation and maintenance cost of the electrolyzer, and C_{rep} is the replacement cost of the electrolyzer, with a lifespan of 7 years [22]:

$$C_{el} = C_{el,u} \times \left(\frac{M_{H_2} \times K_{el,th}}{8760 \times \eta_{elec}} \right), \tag{10}$$

here $C_{el,u}$ is the unit cost of the PEM electrolyzer, $K_{el,th}$ is the theoretical energy required by the electrolyzer to produce 1 kg of hydrogen (52.5 kWh/kg), and η_{elec} is the electrolyzer efficiency set at 75%.

All economic parameters are presented in Table 6.

2.6. Sensitivity analysis

After the final suitability map was produced sensitivity analysis was conducted for both spatial and LCOH₂.

For the spatial, a sensitivity analysis was conducted to evaluate the suitability results by checking how changes in the priority of criteria and sub-criteria affect the final suitability index.

In our study, we compared the impact of modifying weight by adding 20% to each criterion on land suitability [45]. Six sensitivity analysis scenarios (SA) were created. For each scenario, priority was given to one criterion over the others. In SA1, SA3, SA4, and SA5, the weights of climate, water availability, slope, economic utility, and accessibility were amplified for each criterion, respectively. By the following equations, we can adapt the main AHP matrix for each SA scenario [45].

$$W_{c_i,20\%} = (1 + 0.2) \cdot W_{c_i,0\%}, \tag{11}$$

with $W_{c_m,20\%}$ and $W_{c_m,0\%}$ are the modified and unchanged base weights for the criterion-focused for each SA scenario, and all criteria weights should sum to 1. Therefore, it is necessary to recalculate the modified weights of the other criteria as follows:

Table 4
RI value according with Saaty.

n	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
RI	0	0	0.58	0.90	1.12	1.24	1.32	1.41	1.45	1.49

$$W_{c_i,20\%} = \frac{(1 - W_{c_b,20\%}) \cdot W_{c_i,0\%}}{1 - W_{c_b,0\%}}, \tag{12}$$

where $W_{c_i,0\%}$ is the base weight of the $i - th$ criterion.

The sixth scenario considers equal weights for all sub-criteria, assigning the same weight (7.69%) to each sub-criterion [46]. After that, the SA maps were produced, and all results are discussed in Section 3.2.

Regarding the LCOH₂ sensitivity analysis, to evaluate the impact of cost reduction on LCOH₂. In Europe, a study calculated the projection of PV investment cost by 2050 and reduced it to 24% [47]. In our case, we reduced the CAPEX from 100% to 76% with a 5% step. All results are presented in Section 3.2.

3. Results and discussion

This section presents the results of the site suitability analysis, conducted using five main criteria and thirteen sub-criteria. The analysis integrated the AHP method with GIS tools to identify the most suitable zones and to select four hotspots. Subsequently, the economic viability of hydrogen production at these priority sites was assessed using three PV configurations: fixed, 1-axis, and 2-axis PV systems, through a techno-economic analysis.

Table 5
Specific parameters used for PV power plant implementation.

PV Module	
Type	Trina solar TSM-670DE21 (mono c-si)
Maximum power	670 W _{DC}
Nominal efficiency	21.77 %
Maximum power voltage	38.2 V _{DC}
Maximum power current	17.6 A _{DC}
Total module number used	74 594
Inverter	
Type	SMA America SC 4600 UP-US 690V 3850A
Maximum AC Power	4198235 W _{AC}
Maximum DC Power	4272030 W _{DC}
Nominal AC voltage	690 V _{AC}
Maximum DC voltage	1200 V _{DC}
Maximum DC current	4022.63 A _{DC}
Total module inverter used	11
AC/DC ratio	1.08
Total nominal capacity	50 MW_p

Table 6
Cost parameters used in this study.

Parameters	Cost value	References
PV costs		
C_{mod}	0.84 \$/Wp (0.77 €/W)	[10]
C_{Bos}	25% of C_{mod}	
$C_{O\&MofPV}$	5% of C_{mod}	
C_{Tr} (1-axis)	135-700 \$/kWp (124.74-646.83 €/kWp)	[42]
C_{Tr} (2-axis)	600-1900 \$/kWp (554.43-1755.68 €/kWp)	
PEM Electrolyzer cost		
$C_{O\&MofEl}$	2% of C_{el}	[43]
C_{rep}	25% of C_{el}	
$C_{el,u}$	368 \$/kWe (340 €/kWe)	
The conversion factor used from Dollar to Euro is 0.924043614858 [44]		

Table 7
Weight of factors for our power plant.

Criteria	Global Weight %	Sub-criteria	Sub-criteria weights	Classes/ Factors	Weight %		
Climate	40.7	GHI	40.7	1777-1890	40.73		
				1668-1777	30.54		
				1559-1668	20.36		
				1450-1559	10.18		
Orography	16.3	Slope	16.3	<4%	16.25		
				4-8%	12.19		
				8-12%	8.13		
Water resources	29	Distance to water ways	12.62	<5 km	12.62		
				5 km-10km	9.46		
				10 km-15km	6.31		
				>15 km	3.15		
				<20 km	11.34		
				20 km-30km	8.51		
		Distance to sea edge	11.34	3.87	3.87	30 km-50km	5.67
						>50 km	2.84
						<10 km	2.90
		Distance to dams	3.87	1.94	1.94	10 km-15km	1.94
						15 km-25km	0.97
						>25 km	1.16
Distance to groundwater border	1.16	0.87	0.87	on the spot	1.16		
				2.5 km from the border	0.87		
				2.5-5 km	0.58		
Economics	10.2	Population count	5.63	>5 km	0.29		
				>1 000 000	5.63		
				550 000 - 1 000 000	4.22		
				300 000 - 550 000	2.82		
				<300 000	1.41		
				<1 km	2.59		
		Distance to electricity grid	2.59	1.94	1.94	1 km-5km	1.94
						5 km-10km	1.29
						>10 km	0.65
		Distance to gas pipelines	1.44	1.08	1.08	<1.5 km	1.44
						1.5 km-5km	1.08
						5km-7.5 km	0.72
Distance to ports	0.54	0.40	0.40	>7.5 km	0.36		
				<1.5 km	0.54		
				1.5 km-5km	0.40		
Accessibility	3.8	Distance to big cities	2.06	5km-7.5 km	0.27		
				>7.5 km	0.13		
				<1 km	2.06		
				1-5 km	1.54		
				5-20 km	1.03		
				>20 km	0.51		
		Distance to railways	1.14	1.14	1.14	<1 km	1.14
						<1 km	1.14
						<1 km	1.14
						<1 km	1.14
						<1 km	1.14
						<1 km	1.14

This section is structured in three parts: the first presents the site suitability analysis, the second discuss the sensitivity analysis, and the third provides a techno-economic evaluation of hydrogen production at the four selected hotspots.

3.1. Suitability analysis

The primary objective of this study is to identify suitable zones for the installation of large-scale “green” hydrogen power plants across mainland Portugal. To achieve this, an integrated methodological framework was implemented, combining the AHP with GIS-based spatial analysis. This approach enabled the systematic evaluation of five main criteria and thirteen sub-criteria, ensuring a comprehensive assessment of factors influencing site suitability. The relative importance of each criterion and sub-criterion was quantified through the AHP method, and with the Consistency Ratio (CR) reduced to 0.0066 (all AHP matrices, both global and local, are presented in the [Annex 1](#)), the resulting weights were subsequently incorporated into the spatial analysis to generate a suitability map. The climate criterion, represented in this study by the GHI factor, received the highest weight of 40.73%, with priority assigned to areas with the highest irradiation values (1777-1890 kWh/m²). This predominance reflects the critical role of solar resource availability in determining the viability of PV-based hydrogen production. In addition, the slope criterion emerged as another key determinant for site suitability, as relatively flat terrain minimizes the additional costs associated with extensive earthworks required for large-scale PVH2 plants. Following the evaluation process, a weight of 16.25% was assigned to slopes of less than 4%, highlighting the critical role of topographic conditions in the overall site selection process. Water availability is an essential selection criterion for the development of hydrogen production projects, as it is indispensable for the operation of electrolysis facilities. In this study, four types of water sources were considered: waterways, seawater, dams, and underground water. The resulting weightings were 12.62% for sites located less than 5 km from waterways, 11.34% for sites located less than 20 km from the coastline, 3.87% for sites located less than 10 km from dams, and 1.16% for sites located directly above groundwater resources. For the economic criterion, four sub-criteria were considered: population count with 5.63% weight for populations greater than one million people, distance to electricity grid with 2.59% for distances less than 1 km, distance to gas pipelines with 1.44% for distances less than 1.5 km, and distance to ports with 0.53% for distances less than 1.5 km.

The last criterion used is accessibility, with three sub-criteria: distance to big cities with 2.06% for distances less than 1 km, distance to roads with 0.63% for distances less than 1.5 km, and distance to railways with 1.14% for distances less than 1 km.

We note that all sub-criteria were divided into four classes. The excellent value/class of each sub-criterion receives 100% of the total sub-criterion weight. The second, third, and fourth classes receive 75%, 50%, and 25% of the total sub-criterion weight, respectively. For example, for GHI, the excellent class (1777–1890 kWh/m²) receives the

Table 7 (continued)

Criteria	Global Weight %	Sub-criteria	Sub-criteria weights	Classes/ Factors	Weight %				
				1 km-5km	0.85				
				5 km-15km	0.57				
				>15 km	0.28				
				<1.5 km	0.63				
				1.5 km-5km	0.47				
				5km-7.5 km	0.31				
				>7.5 km	0.16				

The suitable zone for the PVH2 plant in Portugal

Fig. 7. PV-based hydrogen power plant suitable atlas.

full weight of 40.73%, while the 1668–1777 kWh/m², 1559–1668 kWh/m², and 1450–1559 kWh/m² classes receive 30.54%, 20.36%, and 10.18%, respectively. All AHP weight results are presented in the following table.

To identify the most suitable areas for PV-based hydrogen power plants, the AHP-derived weights from Table 7 were integrated with GIS tools to assess each pixel across mainland Portugal, excluding the restricted areas shown in Fig. 6. This procedure resulted in the generation of a PVH2 suitability atlas. The resulting map categorizes suitability into four classes: “Highly suitable,” “Suitable,” “Moderately suitable,” and “Marginally suitable,” as presented in Fig. 7. The most relevant area for the present study is the “Highly suitable” class, which represents 1665.7 km² (1.9% of mainland Portugal). This is a well-defined result for the potential development of “green” hydrogen projects. The other classes are as follows: “Suitable” areas represent 10 245.4 km² (11.62% of mainland Portugal), “Moderately suitable” areas cover 2999.1 km² (3.4%), and “Marginally suitable” areas cover 114.7 km² (0.13%). All

Table 8
Land suitability share of mainland Portugal for PVH2.

Suitability	Area (km ²)	
Highly suitable	1665.67	1.89%
Suitable	10 245.40	11.62%
Moderately suitable	2999.09	3.40%
Marginally suitable	114.67	0.13%
Unsuitable/exclusion	73 917.37	82.26%

suitable areas are summarized in Table 8.

3.2. Techno-economic analysis at the most suitable locations

Based on the suitability results from the previous section, four hot-spots were selected from different locations, with a good distribution within the “Highly Suitable” areas, as shown in Fig. 8 (detailed

Table 9
Hotspots main characteristics.

locations	Latitude	Longitude	GHI (kWh/m ² /year)	Weight
Hotspot 1	37.182596	-7.657758	1890	0.868916
Hotspot 2	37.924768	-8.756259	1804	0.844163
Hotspot 3	37.849567	-7.832602	1820	0.797156
Hotspot 4	38.897846	-8.541048	1795	0.788344

information is presented in Table 9). These selected sites aim to evaluate hydrogen production using different PV technologies: fixed, 1-axis, and 2-axis tracking systems with 50 MW_{DC} capacity, and to evaluate the LCOH₂ for each technology.

Hotspot 1 is located in the Algarve region, between Monte Gordo and Vila Real de Santo António. This site has a higher GHI values in Portugal, reaching 1890 kWh/m²/year. Hotspot 2 is near Sines and southern Lisbon, within 7 km by road from the Morgavel solar PV power plant (*Central Fotovoltaica de Morgavel*), with a GHI value of 1804 kWh/m²/year. Hotspot 3 is located in the Alentejo region, 23 km by road from Beja city. This location has a high GHI of 1820 kWh/m²/year. Hotspot 4 is situated in central Portugal, within the Lisbon district, with a GHI value to 1795 kWh/m²/year.

The following table presents the coordinate location and weight calculated for each hotspot.

After the simulation of a 50 MW_{DC} PV-based hydrogen power plant at these hotspots using different technologies, fixed, 1-axis, and 2-axis tracking systems, we found promising results for the future of hydrogen in Portugal.

- Hotspot 1 offers high production, with a maximum in June of 204.41 tons, 272.73 tons, and 283.42 tons, and an average monthly of

136.58 tons, 188.23 tons, and 215.52 tons, respectively, for the three technologies.

- Hotspot 2 provides the highest production, with a maximum in July: 226.36 tons, 308.83 tons, and 323.83 tons, with average values of 140.28 tons, 195.93 tons, and 227.57 tons, respectively.
- Hotspot 3 also provides a high production, with the maximum monthly production is recording in July, with 202.79 tons, 271.72 tons and 283.16 tons, the average monthly production to 131.16 tons, 180.44 tons and 207.31 tons respectively.
- Hotspot 4 also offers high production, with a peak in July of 200.60 tons, 271.99 tons, and 284.47 tons, and average values of 129.75 tons, 178.19 tons, and 204.45 tons, respectively.

All monthly production results are presented in Fig. 9.

These interactive results confirm the reliability of the selected locations, showing high annual hydrogen production at the hotspots using different technologies. This indicates a favourable LCOH₂, as presented in Table 10.

Hotspot 2 offers the best opportunity for “green” hydrogen production in Portugal, using the 1-axis tracking system. It achieves the lowest LCOH₂ of 2.95 €/kg and the highest annual hydrogen production of 2351 tons, corresponding 47.02 kg/kW, making it a promising location for hosting a solar photovoltaic-based hydrogen power plant. This site is near Sines, a city already hosting several renewable energy projects such as the Morgavel Solar PV Power Plant (*Central Fotovoltaica de Morgavel*), and planned hydrogen projects like GreenH2atlantic [48]MadoquaPower2X [49] and H2tALENT [50].

These findings are particularly relevant in the context of Portugal’s energy policy [6], The National Hydrogen Strategy (EN-H2) aims to achieve 2–2.5 GW of renewable-powered electrolysis capacity by 2030 and to supply 1.5–2% of the country’s total energy demand with “green” hydrogen, targeting the industrial sector (2–5% of demand), domestic

Fig. 8. Hotspots of the techno-economic analyses.

Fig. 9. Monthly hydrogen production at the three hotspots.

Table 10
Hydrogen production and LCOH₂ for the hotspots using different technologies.

Locations	Fixed system		1-axis tracking system		2-axis tracking system	
	H ₂ annual production (tons)	LCOH ₂ (€/kg)	H ₂ annual production (tons)	LCOH ₂ (€/kg)	H ₂ annual production (tons)	LCOH ₂ (€/kg)
Hotspot 1	1639	3.77	2259	3.05	2586	3.33
Hotspot 2	1683	3.69	2351	2.95	2731	3.18
Hotspot 3	1574	3.91	2165	3.17	2488	3.45
Hotspot 4	1557	3.95	2138	3.20	2453	3.49

Table 11
Sensitivity analyses AHP results.

Criteria	Sub-criteria	Weight %					
		SA1	SA2	SA3	SA4	SA5	SA6
Climate	GHI	0.488	0.374	0.391	0.398	0.404	7.692
Orography	Slope	0.140	0.149	0.195	0.159	0.161	7.692
Water resources	Distance to water ways	0.109	0.151	0.121	0.123	0.125	7.692
	Distance to sea edge	0.099	0.136	0.109	0.110	0.112	7.692
	Distance to dams	0.033	0.046	0.037	0.038	0.038	7.692
	Distance to groundwater border	0.010	0.014	0.011	0.011	0.012	7.692
Economics	Population count	0.049	0.052	0.054	0.067	0.056	7.692
	Distance to electricity grid	0.022	0.024	0.025	0.031	0.025	7.692
	Distance to gas pipelines	0.012	0.013	0.014	0.017	0.014	7.692
	Distance to ports	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.006	0.005	7.692
Accessibility	Distance to big cities	0.018	0.019	0.020	0.020	0.024	7.692
	Distance to railways	0.010	0.010	0.011	0.011	0.013	7.692
	Distance to roads	0.005	0.006	0.006	0.006	0.007	7.692

maritime shipping (3–5%), and road transportation (1–5%). Additionally, hydrogen is planned to be injected into the natural gas network to reach 10–15% of the delivered gas volume.

In line with these national targets, the Sines port area (near Hotspot 2 identified in this study) has been earmarked by the government for a large-scale hydrogen power plant. As early as 2021, an initial plan proposed the rapid deployment of a 10 MW electrolyzer, with a 2030 target of 1–1.5 GW of capacity. Our results support and further refine this decision by highlighting Hotspot 2 as a highly suitable location for large-scale “green” hydrogen production.

3.3. Sensitivity analysis

This section discusses the results of both sensitivity analyses, spatial and LCOH₂. The spatial sensitivity analysis is used to evaluate the robustness of the site suitability model. Six scenarios are evaluated: SA1 (climate-focused), SA2 (water availability-focused), SA3 (Orography-focused), SA4 (economic utility-focused), SA5 (accessibility-focused), and SA6 (equal sub-criterion weights). Table 11 presents the AHP results for each SA scenario.

After determining the sub-criterion weights for each sensitivity analysis scenario, maps were created for every scenario (see Fig. 10), and the suitability classes of each scenario were calculated and are presented in Table 12. The results indicate that the suitability model is

Fig. 10. Sensitivity analysis maps of six scenarios: (a) climate-focused, (b) water-focused, (c) slope-focused, (d) economic-focused, (e) accessibility -focused, and (f) equal weights.

Table 12
Land suitability area of mainland Portugal for each sensitivity analysis scenario.

Scenario	Highly Suitable (%)	Suitable (%)	Moderately Suitable (%)	Marginally Suitable (%)
SA 1: Solar Focused	2.460	11.573	2.870	0.140
SA 2: Water Focused	1.522	11.489	3.894	0.137
SA 3: Slope Focused	1.878	11.564	3.405	0.195
SA 4: Economic Focused	1.723	11.478	3.700	0.142
SA 5: Accessibility Focused	1.696	11.489	3.711	0.147
SA 6: Equal Weights	0.530	9.176	6.401	0.934

sensitive to topography and technical factors.

Scenario SA1 (climate-focused) yielded the largest “highly suitable” areas, accounting for 2.46% of the total mainland Portugal area. This

indicates that when climate is prioritized, a significant portion of the study area becomes more highly suitable. For SA2, SA3, SA4 and SA5, the “highly suitable” areas are also relatively high at 1.52%, 1.88%, 1.72% and 1.70%, respectively. This highlights the importance of these criteria and demonstrates the stability of our model.

Finally, SA6 (equal weights) evaluates the model under uniform weights without any priority and provides a balanced distribution for all sub-criteria, identifying 9.8% of the area as “suitable.” The results from this scenario confirm that the model is stable and that the identified sites consistently perform well across scenarios.

The next sensitivity analysis focuses on the levelized cost of hydrogen production (LCOH₂). This analysis evaluates the impact of reducing PV investment costs on LCOH₂ for our hotspots, using three PV technologies: fixed, 1-axis, and 2-axis tracking systems, by reducing the investment cost to 76% for each PV technology at each hotspot location. The results show that by 2050, the lowest LCOH₂ is achieved using the 1-axis tracking system, decreasing to 2.62, 2.54, 2.72, and 2.75 €/kg for Hotspot 1, Hotspot 2, Hotspot 3, and Hotspot 4, respectively. Table 13 presents all LCOH₂ sensitivity analysis results.

Table 13
The impact of reducing PV investment costs on LCOH₂.

Reducing PV Investment Costs	LCOH ₂ on Hotspot 1 (€/kg)			LCOH ₂ on Hotspot 2 (€/kg)			LCOH ₂ on Hotspot 3 (€/kg)			LCOH ₂ on Hotspot 4 (€/kg)		
	Fixed	1-Axis	2-Axis									
100 %	3.77	3.05	3.33	3.69	2.95	3.18	3.91	3.17	3.45	3.95	3.20	3.49
95 %	3.66	2.96	3.22	3.58	2.86	3.07	3.80	3.07	3.33	3.84	3.11	3.38
90 %	3.56	2.87	3.1	3.47	2.78	2.97	3.69	2.98	3.22	3.72	3.0	3.26
85 %	3.45	2.79	3.01	3.37	2.69	2.87	3.57	2.89	3.11	3.61	2.92	3.15
80 %	3.34	2.70	2.90	3.26	2.61	2.76	3.46	2.79	2.99	3.49	2.82	3.03
76 %	3.25	2.62	2.81	3.17	2.54	2.68	3.37	2.72	2.90	3.40	2.75	2.94

4. Conclusions

This study shows the most suitable areas for developing a solar photovoltaic-based hydrogen power plant by considering five main criteria, climate, orography, water resources, economic factors, and accessibility, and thirteen sub-criteria. The AHP method combined with GIS tools was applied to mainland Portugal to create the first suitability atlas for PV-H₂ power plants. The suitability atlas is divided into four classes: “Highly suitable”, “Suitable”, “Moderately suitable”, and “Marginally suitable”, indicating highest potential for renewable hydrogen energy and the reduction of CO₂ emissions as an alternative to conventional power plants.

The “Highly suitable” area covers only 1665.67 km² (1.89% of mainland Portugal) but has significant potential for PV-H₂ power plants, providing a spatial basis to help achieve the national target of 2.0–2.5 GW of electrolysis capacity by 2030. A benchmarking analysis was conducted between three PV technologies, fixed, 1-axis, and 2-axis tracking systems, at four hotspots. The PV system with 1-axis tracking technology showed the lowest LCOH₂ values: 3.05 €/kg, 2.95 €/kg, and 3.20 €/kg for Hotspot 1, Hotspot 2, Hotspot 3 and Hotspot 4, respectively, with corresponding annual hydrogen production of 2259 tons, 2351 tons, 2165 tons and 2138 tons.

However, in terms of highest production, the 2-axis tracking system offered the greatest annual hydrogen output: 2586 tons, 2731 tons, 2488, tons and 2453 tons, with LCOH₂ values of 3.33 €/kg, 3.18 €/kg, 3.45 €/kg, and 3.49 €/kg, respectively, for the four hotspots.

For these reasons, we believe our results can support government decision-making for the development of large-scale solar photovoltaic-based hydrogen power plants, particularly at these hotspots or in the main “Highly suitable” areas, to strengthen Portugal's energy supply.

Annex 1.

1. The global AHP matrix

	Climate	Water availability	Slope	Economic utility	Accessibility
Climate	1	1.5	2.5	4.5	9
Water availability	0.7	1	2	3	7
Slope	0.4	0.5	1	1.5	5
Economic utility	0.2	0.3	0.7	1	3
Accessibility	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.3	1

CR = 0.0066

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Mohammed Attiaoui: Writing – original draft, Software, Resources, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Fatima-Zahra Ouchani:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Hugo Gonçalves Silva:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Ahmed Alami Merrouni:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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2. Water availability AHP matrix

	Distance to water ways	Distance to sea edge	Distance to dams	Distance to groundwater border
Distance to water ways	1	1.5	2.5	9
Distance to sea edge	0.7	1	4	8
Distance to dams	0.4	0.3	1	5
Distance to groundwater border	0.1	0.1	0.2	1
CR = 0.0088				

3. Economics AHP matrix

	Population count	Distance to electricity grid	Distance to gas pipelines	Distance to ports
Population count	1	2.5	4	9
Distance to electricity grid	0.4	1	2	5
Distance to gas pipelines	0.3	0.5	1	3
Distance to ports	0.1	0.2	0.3	1
CR = 0.0095				

4. Accessibility AHP matrix

	Distance to big cities	Distance to railways	Distance to roads
Distance to big cities	1	2	3
Distance to railways	0.5	1	2
Distance to roads	0.3	0.5	1
CR = 0.0096			

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